

IDENTIFY THE LEVEL OF INTELLIGENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCHOOL
EDUCATIONAL VIVID GUREVICHNING K. M. “DEVELOPMENT OF SCHOOL
MENTAL TEST” SUBTESTING IMPORTANCE

Narkulov Xusan Ismoilovich

Teacher of the psychology department of Termez State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11127555>

Abstract. According to the source recorded in scientific psychological intelligence is derived from the Latin word, it usually mind-idroq, to realize, to understand means to fahmlab. We, at a certain level of intelligence a person solid, stable to the complex structure of cognitive skills.

Key words: intelligence, psychological testing, nonverbal scale, amtxauer intelligence test.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ПРИ РАЗВИТИИ ШКОЛЬНОГО
УЧЕБНОГО ЯРКОГО ГУРЕВИЧНИНГ К. М. «РАЗРАБОТКА ШКОЛЬНОГО
МЕНТАЛЬНОГО ТЕСТА» ВАЖНОСТЬ СУБТЕСТИНГА

Аннотация. Согласно источнику, зафиксированному в научных источниках, психологический интеллект происходит от латинского слова, обычно разум-идроқ, осознавать, понимать, значит фахмлаб. Мы, на определенном уровне интеллекта, человек твердый, устойчивый к сложной структуре когнитивных навыков.

Ключевые слова: интеллект, психологическое тестирование, невербальная шкала, тест интеллекта Амтксауэра.

INTRODUCTION

According to scientific psychological sources, intelligence is derived from the Latin word, which usually means more intelligent understanding, understanding, understanding. It seems to us that intelligence consists in the structure of a complex of a person's to some extent solid, stable mental abilities. Many classical tests have been playing an important role in determining an individual's level of intelligence.

To summarize the problem research materials collected by members of the intelligence psychologists in the research of attention-attention should be paid to the following factors:

- the period of the age of intelligence depends on the properties of
- affiliated to order and children to come into the world to feature sex,
- folks, etno, nationalities, and people relating to,
- family socio-economic status by a combination,
- ma'lumotlilik of parents, social origin,
- biological shartlangan person's qualities, attributes, qualities play a role in how and so

forth.

Intelligence in psychology, cognitive abilities, and concepts close to it by foreign and domestic scientists on these issues and the interpretation of study status and reader mastering the ability to in the world, affecting psychological, pedagogical attention to factors.

School governors and overall development of the intellectual capacity latest methods are designed to determine the level of psixodiagnostik Gurevichning k. m. “School mental development tests” has the potential to separate. This methodology is subtestdan six. Each subtest

or the settings of this process students thought itvalong with also allows you to determine the level of general ojlanganligini bilimdonlik study.

K.M.Gurevichning School mental development tests” in “Which” and “Synthesis” testsiusing the research was conducted. “Which” and “Synthesis” subtesti tempted by the sum of points collected on the basis of the results of the evaluation of. The assignments for each test is given a score from sticking. The total maximum score is equal to 20. Assessment criteria: 17-20 points high, the average level of 10-16 points, with low levels of less than 9 points will be evaluated.

1-table

“Which” and “Umumilashtirish” test indicators

K. m. Gurevich test	“Which	“Umumilashtirish”
Indicator in percent	76%	72%

1-the picture. “Which,” and “Synthesis” test indicators

This is the “Which” and “synthesis” for the purpose of the research the results from the test were used. 120 high-grade research who participated reader(respondent) s on the average of both tests have come and above participated. This is the environment that is suitable to the scale of the national tests, and readers of the intellectual capabilities that can be used in diagnostics it shows. World intelligence the development of the person as the basis of cognitive ability development made us look at it conducts research on the intellectual development.

The quick exchange of information, information diversity, during the period of modern technologies on the basis of enhancing the intellectual capacity of young people's education, each society in the development of intellectual cultivation of the different sectors of the youth team of the country social, economic, ma'anaviy, the necessity of political power for the consolidation of talented professionals and strategic intelligence for the development of special education in the context of the organization of learning in educational institutions such as the necessity of the necessity of have that look.

In this context, the development of diagnostic features avvvalo opportunities for intellectual development intellectual they require attention to determine the level of development of particular aspects only and then is required to take.

REFERENCES

1. Narkulov, X. I. (2024). TYPES AND FEATURES OF INTELLIGENCE TESTS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(3), 39-41.
2. Narkulov, X. I. (2024). THE CONTENT OF THEIR ACTIVITIES ACCORDING TO THE PSYCHODIAGNOSTIC NATURE OF THE AMTXAUER INTELLIGENCE TEST, WHICH IS PART OF THE INTELLIGENCE TESTS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 186-188.